

**A Heterogeneous Precipitate based Lead(II)
Coated Wire Ion-selective Electrode : Its
Application in the Determination of Stability
Constant of 1 : 1 Lead(II)-Alizarin Red S
Complex**

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IN continuation with the work on ion-selective electrodes (ISE's) in this laboratory¹, the design of novel coated wire ion-selective electrodes (CWISE) is now being attempted.

Though several ISE's for lead have been reported², no successful attempt appears to have been made for the fabrication of CWISE for Pb^{II}. In this communication a heterogeneous precipitate based Pb^{II}-anthranilate CWISE has been described. Its successful application has been demonstrated by making use of the electrode in determining the free Pb^{II} concentration in Pb^{II}-alizarin red S (ARS) complex equilibrium, thereby enabling the determination of stability constant of the 1:1 complex. The values obtained compare well with that determined using the spectrophotometric technique.

Experimental

Preparation of electrode: An aqueous solution of anthranilic acid was neutralised with sodium carbonate, care being taken that the final solution remained slightly acidic. To it lead nitrate (0.5 g) dissolved in water was added to obtain a white precipitate of lead anthranilate³. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with water and dried at room temperature. The dried precipitate (100 mg) was mixed with Araldite (400 mg) and coated on one end of a clean copper wire to obtain a bead⁴. It was dried for 24 h in air. The electrode thus prepared was kept immersed overnight in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ lead nitrate solution.

A Philips PR 9405 M pH meter with a saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode was used. All measurements were made at 30±1°. Double-distilled water was used and the chemicals were of reagent grade.

Measurements were made using the following cell.

Metal	Ion-selective membrane	Sample solution	External reference electrode
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Results and Discussion

The electrode gave a linear response down to a concentration of 5 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 1). The slope of the electrode was 30 mV per decade change in concentration and this remained constant for over a period of 12 weeks.

To find the response time, the electrode was dipped in 0.01 mol dm⁻³ lead nitrate solution and suddenly it was taken out and dipped in 0.001 mol dm⁻³ lead nitrate solution. The values of the potential change were noted every 5 s. A constant potential was obtained after 35 s.

To study the effect of pH, the pH of a 0.01 mol dm⁻³ Pb(NO₃)₂ solution was varied by the addition of NaOH or HCl. It was found that the potential remained unchanged within the pH range 2.8–9.2.

The selectivity coefficient for different cations for Pb^{II} ion was determined by mixed solution method⁶ and it was found that the electrode is selective in presence of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Al^{III}, La^{III}, Cr^{III}, Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} ions (Table 1 ; Fig. 1).

TABLE 1—ELECTRODE SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS ($k_{Pb,M}^{pot}$) DETERMINED BY MIXED SOLUTION METHOD

Cation (M)	$k_{Pb,M}^{pot}$
Co ^{II}	0.0
Al ^{III}	0.050
Cr ^{III}	0.010
La ^{III}	0.050
Zr ^{IV}	0.008
Th ^{IV}	0.008

Application: Ion-selective electrodes have been used in the direct determination of the free metal ion concentration in metal-ligand equilibria⁶. The stability constant of a complex in solution can be

Fig. 1. Electrode response and selectivity coefficients of Pb^{II} electrode.

evaluated therefrom. The stability constant of the 1:1 Pb^{II}-ARS complex has been determined to illustrate the use of Pb^{II} electrode, using a new method of calculation.

Two sets of solutions were prepared. In the first set, the metal ion and ligand concentrations were kept constant and the pH was varied in the range 3.0–5.0. In the second set, the pH was kept constant at 4.5 and the ligand concentration was varied keeping the metal ion concentration constant. An ionic strength of 0.1 was maintained using sodium perchlorate. For each solution, the free metal ion concentration was determined from the potential measurements using the electrode. An account of the method adopted is given below :

Theory : In a metal-ligand equilibrium,

$$K_1'' = \frac{[ML][H]^n}{[M][H_n L]} \quad (2)$$

where, K_1'' is a conditional stability constant and can be defined at a particular ionic strength,

$$K_1' = \frac{[ML]}{[M][H_n L]} = \frac{K_1''}{[H]^n} \quad (3)$$

Now the stability constant is defined as

$$K_1 = \frac{[ML]}{[M][L]} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } K_1 = K_1' \phi \quad (5)$$

where,

$$\phi = \left(1 + \frac{[H]}{K_{a1}} + \frac{[H]^2}{K_{a1}K_{a2}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where K_{a1} and K_{a2} are respectively the first and second dissociation constants of ligands. Equation (6) can be multiplied by a correction factor (F) to take into account the hydrolysis of the metal M . F is given by

$$F = \left(1 + \frac{K_{h1}}{[H]} + \frac{K_{h1} \cdot K_{h2}}{[H]^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

where K_{h1} and K_{h2} are respectively the first and second hydrolysis constant of Pb^{II}.

For 1:1 complex, the metal-ligand equilibrium can be expressed as

$$K_1' = \frac{[ML]}{(M^0 - [ML])(L^0 - [ML])} \quad (8)$$

where M^0 and L^0 are the total metal and ligand concentrations respectively. Equation (8) can be rearranged as

$$\frac{[M]}{M^0 - [M]} = \frac{1}{K_1' L^0} + \frac{[M]}{L^0} \quad (9)$$

This equation may be considered under two different conditions : (i) where pH remains constant and (ii) where pH is varied.

At constant pH, equation (9) can be rearranged as

$$\frac{[M]L^0}{M^0 - [M]} = \frac{1}{K_1'} + [M] \quad (10)$$

Thus a plot of $[M]L^0/(M^0 - [M])$ against $[M]$ would give a straight line with slope value as one and intercept as $1/K_1'$ (Fig. 2). The stability constant (K_1) then can be calculated from equation (6). The true value of the stability constant can be obtained by multiplying this value with F .

Fig. 2 Determination of stability constant of Pb^{II}-ARS complex. Plot of $[M]L^0/(M^0 - [M])$ vs $[M]$; final concn. of Pb^{II} = 5.0×10^{-8} mol dm⁻³, ligand varying = $5.0 - 25.0 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.5 (constant), $\phi = 1.41 \times 10^8$, $F = 1.00175$, temp. = 30°, $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO₄); slope = 1.008, intercept = 1.88×10^{-4} , $\log K_1 = 13.62$.

At varying pH, K_1' and F would vary and K_1' can be expressed as

$$K_1' = \frac{K_1(\text{true})}{\phi F} \quad (11)$$

From equations (9) and (11) one can arrive at equation (12),

$$\frac{[M]}{M^0 - [M]} \cdot \frac{1}{\phi F} = \frac{1}{K_1(\text{true}) L^0} + \frac{[M]}{\phi F} \cdot \frac{1}{L^0} \quad (12)$$

If the total metal and ligand concentration are kept constant, a plot of $\frac{[M]}{M^0 - [M]} \cdot \frac{1}{\phi F}$ against $\frac{[M]}{\phi F}$ would give a straight line with slope equal to $1/L^0$ and intercept equal to $1/K_1(\text{true}) L^0$ (Fig. 3) thus enabling one to calculate the true value of stability constant of a 1:1 complex.

From the value of free metal ion concentration and other parameters, the stability constant value of the complex was calculated, and the results are summarised in Figs. 2 and 3. For comparison, the stability constant of the Pb^{II}-ARS complex was determined by spectrophotometry using the graphical method described by Chattopadhyaya⁷. The value of $\log K_1$ comes out to be 13.51 which agrees with the value determined by the use of CWISE.

Fig. 3. Determination of stability constant K_1 of Pb^{II}-ARS complex. Plot $\frac{[M]}{M^o - [M]} \cdot \frac{t}{\phi F}$ vs $\frac{[M]}{\phi F}$; final concn. of Pb^{II} = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, final concn. of ligand = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH varying, $K_{a1} = 9.77 \times 10^{-12}$, $K_{a2} = 2.8 \times 10^{-6}$, temp. = 30°, $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO₄), $K_{h1} = 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$, $K_{h2} = 3.98 \times 10^{-6}$; slope = 1.78×10^6 , intercept = 0.114×10^{-6} , $\log K_1 = 13.19$.

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